

El Gordo: a massive blow to Λ CDM cosmology

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Galaxy clusters are the largest gravitationally bound structures in the Universe. When these structures form is highly dependent on the cosmological model, and thus on the assumed gravitational law. The correct model must be able to statistically predict the cosmological epochs at which different structures can be observed.

In recent years, improvements in the quality and resolution of telescopes have made it possible to observe objects which are very deep in space. The mass and velocity of some of these objects turned out to be significantly higher than what the standard model of cosmology (Λ CDM) predicted. A particularly extreme example of this is the galaxy cluster ACT-CL J0102-4915, also known as “El Gordo”.

Figure 1: A composite image showing El Gordo in X-ray light from NASA’s Chandra X-ray Observatory (blue), along with optical data (red, green, and blue) from the European Southern Observatory’s Very Large Telescope (VLT), and infrared emission from NASA’s Spitzer Space Telescope (red and orange). Notice the twin tails towards the upper right. Credits: X-ray: NASA, CXC, Rutgers, J. Hughes et al.; Optical: ESO, VLT and SOAR, Rutgers, F. Menanteau; IR: NASA, JPL, Rutgers, F. Menanteau. Image taken from [3].

El Gordo is an interacting galaxy cluster at redshift $z = 0.87$ composed of two infalling subclusters of total mass $M_{200} \approx 3 \times 10^{15} M_{\odot}$. Other particularities of this cluster are its strong Sunyaev-Zel’dovich (SZ) effect and its strong X-ray luminosity, which is distributed in a single peak and two faint tails (see Figure 1). Both of these suggest that the subclusters are infalling onto each other at a considerable velocity. In our paper “A massive blow for

Λ CDM – the high redshift, mass, and collision velocity of the interacting galaxy cluster El Gordo contradicts concordance cosmology” [1], we statistically quantified how likely it is for this galaxy cluster to arise in the Λ CDM cosmology, and thus whether El Gordo poses a challenge to this model.

Method

In order to find out the likelihood of observing an El Gordo-like object in Λ CDM, we searched for El Gordo analogues in the N -body Jubilee Hubble Volume (Jubilee[§]) cosmological simulation [2]. With a co-moving simulation volume of $(6 h^{-1} \text{ co-moving Gpc (cGpc)})^3$, Jubilee is one of the largest Λ CDM cosmological simulations available at present. A very large simulation box is needed to search for objects as extreme as El Gordo, but a larger simulation box generally implies a decrease in the resolution. Therefore, we cannot attempt to find analogues to El Gordo that match some of its more detailed properties, e.g. its two-tailed X-ray morphology. However, we can still look for a pair of halos whose mass, mass ratio, and infall velocity could potentially give rise to a structure that reproduces the observed characteristics of El Gordo. That is, we can search for the El Gordo progenitors.

The properties of the El Gordo progenitors had already been investigated in previous studies, which used idealised hydrodynamical simulations to constrain the values of these parameters. In this project, we used the results of [4] as they present one of the most recent and most accurate hydrodynamical simulations of El Gordo. After running 123 simulations for different parameters, these authors concluded that the parameter values of the El Gordo progenitors that provide the best fit to observations are: total mass $M_{\text{tot}} = 3.19 \times 10^{15} M_{\odot}$, mass ratio 3.6, and infall velocity $V_{\text{infall}} = 2500 \text{ km/s}$.

Statistical analysis

We compared all infalling pairs of halos identified in the Jubilee simulation at $z = 1$ (since we are looking for analogues to the El Gordo progenitors, the redshift at which we search for them must be slightly higher than that at which El Gordo is observed). We chose as analogues those pairs which match the properties of mass ratio and infall velocity constrained by [4]. There are no cluster pairs in the Jubilee simulation which are massive enough to match the estimated total mass of El Gordo, so we inferred the number of El Gordo analogues by extrapolating the mass function of lower mass ‘analogues’ which satisfy the other criteria. To obtain the redshift dependence, we repeated the same procedure for redshifts $z = 0.5$ and $z = 0$. After taking into account that the volume in which El Gordo was first observed is significantly smaller than the Jubilee simulation box, we were able to obtain

[§]<https://jubilee.ft.uam.es/>

Figure 2: Plot showing the probability of finding El Gordo progenitors in the Λ CDM model at each position in the grid, which we constructed for many values of the cosmic scale factor a (x -axis) and total mass in \log_{10} scale (y -axis). The point in the grid corresponding to the \tilde{M} and a values of the El Gordo progenitors is marked with a red X. Observing an even more extreme pair has a probability of 7.51×10^{-10} (6.16σ), the total probability beyond the solid red contour. Reproduced from Fig. 7 of [1].

the probability of observing an El Gordo-like structure with the observed total mass and cosmic scale factor $a \equiv 1/(1+z)$ (see Figure 2).

Results

The results of our statistical analysis show that the probability of observing an object as extreme as El Gordo in the survey volume in which it was originally found is 7.51×10^{-10} (6.16σ) in the Λ CDM cosmology. The probability is even lower if we account for the fact that other problematic objects for Λ CDM have also been observed, e.g. the Bullet Cluster. From the statistical analysis of [5], we inferred that the probability of observing the Bullet Cluster in its survey region is 5.40×10^{-3} (2.78σ). Combining the probability of having found both El Gordo and the Bullet Cluster in their respective survey regions, we obtained that Λ CDM is in 6.43σ tension with observations.

We considered several possibilities that might alleviate this tension. A lower mass and/or velocity could increase the probability of finding analogues in the Λ CDM cosmological simulation, but the parameters have to be consistent with the high luminosity and brightness observed for El Gordo, which imply a very energetic interaction between its two subclusters. After repeating the analysis for lower masses and velocities, we found that

Λ CDM is still in $> 5\sigma$ tension for every plausible mass and velocity. Another possibility is that the statistics obtained from the Jubilee simulation could be uncertain due to Poisson noise, but this seems unlikely as the mass function that we got from Jubilee is based on 15035 pairs, making the Poisson noise extremely small. We also considered if a different fit to the mass function could significantly affect the final result, but after testing several different fits, we concluded that the results are not greatly affected by this.

El Gordo in ν HDM

In light of our results, we conclude that the observations of very large and/or high velocity clusters at high redshift – such as El Gordo and the Bullet Cluster – cannot be explained in a Λ CDM context. Because of this, we propose an alternative cosmological model in which these observations can be explained naturally: the neutrino-Hot Dark Matter (ν HDM) model [6, 7]. This model assumes MONDian gravity [8] and sterile neutrinos as hot dark matter. In MOND, there is an enhancement to Newtonian gravity at accelerations below $a_0 = 1.2 \times 10^{-10}$ m/s². Therefore, ν HDM predicts that smaller structures assembled together to form larger structures faster than in Λ CDM. [9] performed a series of cosmological simulations using the ν HDM model to examine the formation of galaxy clusters. In their $(0.512 h^{-1} \text{ cGpc})^3$ simulation box, they found about 1 El Gordo analogue, which corresponds to 1.16 analogues in the survey volume. Thus, ν HDM predicts the right order of magnitude for the number of El Gordo-like objects that should be observed in the surveyed region.

Conclusions

The model parameters of the El Gordo progenitors obtained from the hydrodynamical simulations of [4] contradict Λ CDM at 6.16σ based on the Jubilee cosmological simulation. The tension rises to 6.43σ if we also consider the Bullet Cluster, even before considering other known extreme objects. However, El Gordo can be naturally explained in the ν HDM cosmological model.

References

- [1] Asencio, E., et al. 2021, MNRAS, 500, 5249
- [2] Watson, W.A., et al. 2013, MNRAS, 433, 1230
- [3] NASA mission pages: Chandra, accessed: 15/08/2021
- [4] Zhang, C., et al. 2015, ApJ, 813, 129
- [5] Kraljic, D. & Sarkar, S. 2015, JCAP 04, 050
- [6] Angus, G.W. 2009, MNRAS, 394, 527
- [7] Haslbauer, M., et al. 2020, MNRAS, 499, 2845
- [8] Milgrom, M. 1983, ApJ, 270, 365
- [9] Katz, H., et al. 2013, ApJ, 772, 10

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